

**REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY OF PUNTI, *PUNTIUS*
SOPHORE IN RAJHDHALA BEEL, NETRAKONA**

MS Thesis

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Mymensingh

December (2021)
(Examination held in November 2022)

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Submitted to
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In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of

Master of Science
in
Fisheries Management

by

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ABSTRACT

To identify the breeding season of Pool barb, *Puntius sophore* through observation of the gonadosomatic index (GSI), fecundity, oocytes diameter, and gonadal histology of the species and to suggest management recommendations, the reproductive biology was studied with individuals of the population from Rajdhala beel, Netrakona from July 2020 to June 2021. The fish specimens were collected monthly using a seine net. Three methods were employed to determine the spawning season. It is worth mentioning that, the monthly mean gonadosomatic index was found highest in June. Since the mean gonadosomatic index was highest in June, therefore it was opined that the spawning took place in June apparently. Various developmental stages of ovaries were classified considering their external features and the macroscopic views of eggs. The stages were immature, developing, maturing, and spawning. External morphology and macroscopic observation of female gonads showed that the spawning season of pool barb was between March and June. The microscopic examinations of gonad histology detected the presence of five stages of oocyte maturity which were early perinucleolus, yolk vesicle stage, primary yolk stage, migratory nucleus stage, and premature stage. Monthly plotting of percent data of histological stages revealed that the most advanced stage detected in this study occurred in April, May, and June. Based on histological investigation it was eventually concluded that the spawning season of *P. sophore* existed from April to June. Postovulatory follicles and hydrated eggs were absent in the mature ovaries over the study period which gave the support that *P. sophore* was a synchronous single spawner. The study also demonstrated that the standard length of the youngest female that bore mature eggs was 3056 mm, and its gonadosomatic index was 7.48. The range of relative fecundity was from 540 to 4352 per gm of mature females in terms of standard length having a range from 56 mm to 92 mm. Standard length and fecundity yielded a cubic relationship, the equation was $F = 0.0232SL^{2.6877}$ ($r^2 = 0.8683$). The relationship between fecundity and body weight was in the form of a straight line, and the estimated equation was $F = 213.44BW + 125.24$ ($r^2 = 0.892$). High values of coefficients of determination in both cases described strong relationships between predictor and response variables in fecundity estimation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BFRI	:	Bangladesh Fisheries Research Institute
BW	:	Body Weight
DoF	:	Department of Fisheries
FL	:	Fork Length
GDP	:	Gross Domestic Product
GSI	:	Gonadosomatic Index
GW	:	Gonad Weight
SIS	:	Small Indigenous Species
SL	:	Standard Length
TL	:	Total Length

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is a South Asian subtropical country with a land area of 1,47,570 square kilometres and abundant fisheries resources. Inland fisheries and aquaculture play a significant role in Bangladesh's economy in terms of national income, employment, and foreign exchange profits. It is endowed with vast and varied aquatic resources in the form of rivers, canals, flood plain, ponds, lakes, haors, baors, beels, lagoons, inundated paddy fields, estuaries and a long coast line. There are approximately 47,12,205 ha. of inland water areas, with 38,90,282 ha. of open waters and 8,21,923 ha. of closed water, producing 1.23 million MT and 2.48 million MT, respectively (DoF, 2019). In closed waters, the total area of pond and ditches are 397,775 ha. which is the main source of inland production. Fish and fisheries are indispensable part in the life and livelihoods of the people of Bangladesh since time immemorial. It has been playing a vital role in the area-based economy of Bangladesh, contributing about 3.5% to national GDP, 25.72% to agricultural production, 1.23% to export earnings, and providing full-time and part-time employment activities to 17.80 million people (DoF, 2019). Inland fisheries play an important role by providing 83.73% of the total fish production. In addition, Bangladesh is blessed with the world's richest and most diverse inland aquatic ecosystem having a wide variety of living aquatic resources. But over the years, due to natural and manmade hazards, aquatic bio-diversity especially species diversity of fish and other aquatic organisms in open water have been declining rapidly (Mollah, 2005). Moreover, overfishing may result in reduction of fish population; alternation of food chain and biodiversity.

In Bangladesh, changes in the overall agricultural system, especially rice production, as well as in the use of land and water cause continued decline in the areas of inland water and inundation, reducing the habitats for fish and cutting off migratory routes from breeding grounds. This has contributed to decreased fish intake, in particular SIS intake among the rural poor (Thompson *et al.*, 2002).

Small indigenous fish species are important from the viewpoint of providing nutrition, subsistence and supplemental income to rural poor people in Bangladesh. Small fish are a common food and an integral part of the everyday carbohydrate rich diets of many population groups in poor countries. These communities are also malnourished, with vitamin deficiencies—the "hidden hunger". Small fish species, as well as the little oil, vegetables and spices with which they are cooked enhance diet diversity. Small fish are a rich source of animal protein, essential fatty acids, vitamins and minerals. Studies in rural Bangladesh and Cambodia showed that small fish made up 50-80 percent of total fish intake in the peak fish production season. Although consumed in small quantities, the frequency of small fish intake was high. As many small fish species are eaten whole, with head, viscera and bones, they are particularly rich in bioavailability of calcium, and some are also rich in vitamin A, iron and zinc (Bogard *et al.*, 2015). Nutrient analysis of common Bangladesh SIS such as punti have shown that they contain much higher vitamin A, calcium and iron than do cultured fish (Bogard *et al.*, 2015). Instead, by eating various waste products, this species acts as a water refiner as well as an insect and bloom controller. Many carnivorous species, including snakeheads, rely on them for food, but the species has declined as a result of habitat degradation, including breeding grounds, increased fishing pressure from an ever-increasing rural population, and the use of pesticide on agricultural land, among other factors.

Rajdhala beel is one of the most important beels in Bangladesh having an area of 53 hectare known for its rich ichthyofauna (Rahman and Haque, 2008). A large number of people from 4 surrounding villages are getting benefits from the fisheries resources of the beel. Over the years, due to environmental deterioration and over-fishing, many of the species became critically endangered and vulnerable in the beel. Punti is one of the most dominant species in the beel having a significant contribution (about 20%) to the annual fish production (Rahman and Haque, 2008). Moreover, punti (*Puntius sophore*) has a great dominance in the total catch from beel. Indicatively, revealing the reproductive pattern of the population can aid the management of this species in this beel.

There are about 260 fresh water fish species, 486 marine fish species, 12 exotic fish species, 24 fresh water shrimp species and 36 marine shrimp species in Bangladesh, among 260 fresh water fish species over 140 have been classified as small indigenous species (SIS) (DoF, 2019). Punti (*P. sophore*) is a small indigenous fish species. It is considered a tasty and nutritious fish having a good market demand. The fish was widely and abundantly available in inland waters of Bangladesh (Rahman, 2005; Talwar and Jhingran, 1991). The total inland capture production from the beels was 98,117 MT in the year 2017-18 (DoF, 2019).

It is one of the small indigenous fish species under the family Cyprinidae found in both fresh and brackish water in Bangladesh. It is a benthopelagic fish and its ability to occupy a variety of habitat such as small streams, ponds, ditch, beel, water logged bodies and inundated fields (Rahman, 2005). SIS enjoy the status of being a preferred, everyday food, well-liked by all household members and with a high frequency of consumption. The punti fish used as food in Bangladesh which are mostly consumed by the lower-class consumers (Samad *et al.*, 2010). This, coupled with the positive perceptions of some small fish species as being good for nutrition and health, as well as reports that a dish made with small fish is more equitably shared among all household members (in contrast to one made with large fish) can be capitalized on to promote the consumption of micronutrient-rich fish species, especially in vulnerable population groups such as young children, pregnant and lactating women, the sick and elderly.

Furthermore, this species acts as a water refiner through consuming various waste materials and also act as insect and bloom controller. Many carnivorous species and some snakehead also depend on them for their food but this species has declined due to loss of natural habitat including breeding grounds, increased fishing pressure from a continually growing rural population, use of insecticide in agricultural land etc. In developing countries with fish resources, fish and fisheries play an important role in the livelihoods, income and diets of many, especially the rural poor, who also suffer from under nutrition, including micronutrient-vitamin and mineral-deficiencies, termed "hidden hunger". It is estimated that 190 million children worldwide are affected by vitamin-A deficiency; two billion people have

an insufficient iodine intake; 1.6 billion (almost 25 percent) of the world's population are anaemic, half of this due to iron deficiency; and many suffer from zinc deficiency (WHO, 2011).

These deficiencies increase the risk of morbidity and mortality from diarrhoea and measles, cause xerophthalmia and anaemia, and negatively affect growth and cognitive development in children, reproductive performance and work productivity. It is estimated that maternal and child under nutrition accounts for 11 percent of total Global Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs), with dire consequences for national and global development (Black *et al.*, 2008).

According to a recent nutrition survey, approximately 30,000 children are becoming blind each year due to vitamin-A deficiency in this country (Thilsted *et al.*, 1997). Therefore, it is urgently necessary to take appropriate measures to conserve these fish species by knowing their biology, improving their habitats, and thereby recommending appropriate management measures. In Bangladesh, a very little biological information on the fisheries biology of inland fishes is available, including most of commercial important species. Moreover, there is an urgent need to manage and regulate the small-scale inland capture fishery by knowing the basic information of population dynamics for the target species (Santos *et al.*, 1995).

In order to the assessment and management of fish stocks, spatial and temporal changes of number and weight in stock should be studied. Reproduction is initial points of these changes. The act or process of reproducing, specifically: the process by which plants and animals give rise to offspring and which fundamentally consists of the segregation of a portion of the parental body by a sexual or an asexual process and its subsequent growth and differentiation into a new individual.

Each fish species has evolved in response to a unique set of selective pressures; hence species often differ in their life-history strategies; each life-history strategy is a set of developmental adaptations that allows a species to achieve evolutionary success. Each life-history stage (i.e., egg, larva, juvenile, adult) has a number of

possible alternative states, but the life history of a given species consists of only one of these states for each life-history period.

Since each fish species evolves under a unique set of ecological conditions, it has a unique reproductive strategy with special adaptations including anatomical adaptations, developmental adaptations, behavioural adaptations, physiological adaptations, and energetic adaptations.

The reproductive process allows species to perpetuate themselves. Almost all fishes reproduce sexually, thus permitting mixing of the genes of the two sexes. The reproductive processes of fishes form the basis for early life history studies. The great variety of these processes among fishes make their study worthwhile, but also determine how early life-history studies of various fishes can be conducted. For example, fishes reproduce in fresh and marine waters, have external and internal fertilization, have short annual reproductive periods, or produce gametes at regular intervals throughout the year. This study summarizes the reproductive patterns of fishes, with an emphasis on how these patterns affect early life-history studies.

In life history of a fish species two major events are very important. One is reproduction another is recruitment. In fisheries studies, the particular event of interest in the reproductive cycle of fish species is time of spawning, when fully developed gametes are released. Study about reproductive biology of any fish is essential for evaluating the condition of its stock, life history, culture practice and actual management of its fishery (Lagler, 1956; Doha and Hye, 1970). Potentiality of reproduction of a population is one of the basic exigencies to designate the individuals of that population in respect to their gonadal conditions (Jhingran and Verma, 1972). It is important to assess the yearly breeding cycle of a fish species for successful fish culture. Spawning of fish occurs during a particular phase of reproductive cycle. Some of them breed once annually while some at regular intervals throughout the year. Knowledge of gonadal development and the spawning season of a species allow subsequent studies on spawning frequency of its population, which is important for its management. Another identification of the breeding activity of an exploited fish species provides management option for protection of its spawning stocks (Laroche and Richardson, 1988). Reproductive

parameters do not provide direct evidence of stock structure, but do provide information to assist in understanding biological processes that may be responsible for maintaining the underlying stock structure of a species. The most important aspect of reproduction is fecundity estimation. Reproductive studies have been important component of the biological basis of management for fish and fisheries. This study is undertaken to determine the spawning season, to estimate fecundity, the size at sexual maturity, age and pattern of egg release of punti fish.

The fish species, *Puntius sophore*, one of the Cyprinid fishes under the family Cyprinidae are mostly available in ponds, small streams, beels, inundated fields and weedy ditches (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991a; Rahman, 1989, 2005) and largely distributed in Asia: Pakistan, India, Nepal, Bangladesh, Myanmar and Yunnan, China (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991b), Bhutan and Afghanistan (Petr, 1999). Moreover, they also remain in domestic aquaria and become mature at 7 to 8 cm (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991a).

The English name of this fish species is pool barb and is locally known as Jati punti in Bangladesh. This is one of the most common, small-sized fishes caught in large quantities from various freshwater habitats. Morphologically, the body of Punti is elongated and compressed laterally with pointed head. Lower jaw is longer. The number of scales on the lateral line series are 20 to 25. The number of scales above the lateral line is 8 to 10. Scales number below the lateral line is 3 to 4. Scales number on the lateral line series mentioned by other writers are: 24 - 26 scales (Rahman, 2005), 22-27 scales (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991a).

Figure 1 *Puntius sophore*

This small fish is well regarded as a quality food containing high amount of Vit- A, protein, zinc, calcium and mineral etc. (Bogard *et al.*, 2015). In spite of having enormous economic and nutritional importance of this species to the rural and urban people as well as the fishing community, adequate studies on their reproductive biology, namely spawning season, minimum length at maturity and fecundity of this species are needed for appropriate management.

Reproductive biology is an important parameter to determine the quality and quantity of fish stock in a natural waterbody as well as to determine the reproductive potential (King, 2013). Successful reproduction and recruitment ensure the sustainability of a fish stock in a natural waterbody.

As punti is self-recruiting species in Rajdhala beel, a biological study can help to make decisions for maintaining its sustainability under the conditions of climatic change and natural productivity (Rahman and Haque, 2008). It is very important to know the effects of environmental variabilities and natural productivity on reproductive biology of this fish. Knowing the biology, the findings of the current study will be helpful in developing good management strategies as well as getting mitigation measures to increase the productivity of punti in order to maintain optimum stock and sustainable higher production benefiting the poor fisheries stakeholders around the area to a greater extent.

In view of the above facts, the present study was undertaken on the reproductive biology of Pool barb (*P. sophore*) with the following objectives:

1. To determine the monthly gonadosomatic indices of the species
2. To determine the fecundity of the species
3. To estimate the spawning season of the species

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Before conducting any experiment, it is important to analyse previous research work relevant to the intended subject. The reproductive biology of punti is not well documented, but there is a few research on certain elements of the biology of several small fishes. The mentioned literature has limitations because there are few connections between it and the current study's scope and objectives. However, the suggested work's associated literature is examined. Despite the abundance of research on spawning frequency, breeding season, and fecundity of several fishes, knowledge on the reproductive biology of *Puntius sophore* is scarce. The following information on the spawning frequencies, breeding season, and fecundity of related fishes that has been gathered from previous studies up to the present:

2.1 Breeding biology of *Puntius* spp.

According to Bhuiyan (1964), during the monsoon season, *Puntius sophore* reproduces. Male fish grow a bright red band along the middle of both flanks during the breeding season. In female fish, this is less obvious.

Shafi and Quddus (1974a) observed that punti, *Puntius stigma*, with a short life cycle, lived only for a year or two and attained maturity very early. The sex ratio indicated that 60% of the fish were males and males were more numerous at lower length-groups (4-7 cm) and females in the higher group (8 cm and above).

In another study, Shafi and Quddus (1974b) studied the fecundity of common punti, *Puntius stigma*, from Bangladesh waters and noted that the fecundity varied from 1,242 to 6,831. The relationship between fecundity and gonad weight was more significant than that of fecundity with other factors.

Mustafa (1991) observed the fecundity and spawning frequency of *Puntius chola* in pond condition and reported that the fecundity of *Puntius chola* was 1,404 to 1,872 with an average of $1,581 \pm 142$. He also observed that the species had at least two distinct group of eggs in the ovary two breeding seasons.

In another study, Sobhana and Nadir (1974) observed the breeding season of *Puntius sarana* in Veli lake, Trivandrum extended from late May to November. Peak spawning occurred in July and October. Gonadosomatic index of both sexes showed the highest value in June and September and the fish matured at 183 mm in total length. The ova diameter frequency inferred that these fishes could breed twice a year (May and September).

The maturity and fecundity of *Puntius sarana* were also studied by Sinha (1975) at Loni Reservoir, India. He reported the presence of a single batch of mature eggs with a mean model size of 99 mm. The cycle of maturation and coefficient of maturation indicated the spawning season of this fish was July-August. Fecundity of the species has been estimated to range from 58.327 to 139.984 with a total length of 230 to 326 mm. The fecundity of *Puntius sarana* with a length of 155 to 250 mm was found to range from 18,925 to 78,929. The mathematical relationships between fecundity and total length, fecundity and body weight, and fecundity and ovary weight were linear, whereas a curvilinear relationship was noted between fecundity and the standard length of the fish.

According to Srivastava (2003), maximum value of gonadosomatic index was 1.849 of male and 12.075 for female in the month of July. The length at maturity was measured as 58 mm for the male and 66 mm for the female for *Puntius sophore*, which was discovered to be a single spawner in a year. Fish length, fish weight, ovary length, and ovary weight were found to have linear relationships with fecundity. Fecundity was significantly correlated with ovarian weight ($r^2 = 0.95479$), fish length ($r^2 = 0.91047$), and fish length ($r^2 = 0.88959$) but not with ovary weight ($r^2 = 0.73668$) or fish length ($r^2 = 0.88959$). This demonstrates that ovarian and fish length and weight both affect fertility.

Mitra *et al.* (2005) investigated length weight relation, reproductive characters and condition of *Puntius sophore* (Hamilton) from a floodplain wetland in West Bengal. This study found that while males considerably deviated from cube law, females followed it. The females matured when they were 61-65 mm in length. The gender ratio was slightly in women's favour (av. 1:1.2). The fish had a fecundity of between 759 (85 mm and 7.66g size) and 29.650 (113 mm and 25.25g size). The diameter of

the ova varied from 0.16 to 0.86 mm. The fish's spawning season lasted from February to August.

Marina (2006) studied the reproductive biology and *Puntius sophore* of a perennial water body in Bangladesh. She suggested that the spawning seasons of *Puntius sophore* were started from April and continued up to September.

Puntius sophore was a single spawned and its spawning frequency or strategy was synchronous type. The minimum standard length (SL) at maturity was 51 mm, and the mean SL at first reproduction estimated from the Logistic model was 66.5 mm for females. Fecundity estimates were 3494 to 31723 eggs from females of 23 to 91 mm standards length. The relations between fecundity (F) and standard length (SL), and between fecundity and body weight (BW) were estimated as $F = 0.00109SL$. ($r^2 = 0.708$) and $F = 1105.645BW - 1709.041$ ($r^2 = 0.948$) respectively.

Tareque *et al.* (2008), studied the aspects of biology of *Puntius sophore* sampled from Mouri river, Khulna, Bangladesh. The mean weight of the bilobed gonads (WG) was 1.36 0.438 g. At the anterior, central, and posterior portions of both lobes, the mean ova diameter was 6.50.51 mm, 6.50.68 mm, and 6.310.56 mm, respectively. Fecundity ranged from 743 to 4013. (LT: 7.0-9.9 cm, W: 5.3-14.3 g). Positive but shaky connections existed between LT-F and W-F. The WG-F link was extremely solid. In August, the GSI was 15.25 ± 3.80 .

Mannan *et al.* (2010) observed the gonad development and reproductive cycle of *Puntius filamentosus* and observed that the spawning month of November and April coincided with North-East Monsoon (November) and South-West Monsoon (April) in India. The gross morphology of *P. filamentosus* showed 6 ovarian stages. The histological appearance of the ovaries showed ten stages (oogonia to atretic oocytes). The testes of *P. filamentosus* showed five morphological stages each. The progression of gonadal cycle of *P. filamentosus* collectively revealed that the maturation of males coincided with the maturation of females during the spawning period.

Bithy *et al.* (2013) estimated the fecundity of Jat punti (*Puntius sophore*) from the experimental ponds of the Field Laboratory Complex, Faculty of Fisheries,

Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh. The estimated fecundity for the three fish groups was 7951 to 17670; 8135 to 23053; and 12461 to 15105 eggs, with a mean gonadosomatic index (GSI) of 23.44 2.50; 30.47 4.52; and 28.43 2.99, respectively. The association between fecundity and total length was linear, with $\ln F = 1634 \ln TL - 1972$, $\ln F = 119405 \ln TL - 273.53$, and $\ln F = 1831.6 \ln TL + 825.31$, of three groups respectively. The linear regression equation between body weight and total length was $\ln W = 2.2128 \ln TL - 0.7048$, $\ln W = 2.0207 \ln TL + 0.3493$, and $\ln W = 1.4438 \ln TL + 5.5694$, respectively, in 3 group. The linear regression equation between body weight and fecundity was $F = 656.84 W + 199.96$, $F = 438.16 W + 2470$, and $F = 1116.1 W - 3433.5$, respectively. The total length and body weight were closely linked with fecundity, suggesting that *P. sophore* was a moderately fecund fish.

Using direct observation of sexual features (e.g., gonadosomatic index) and the indirect method of relative growth, Ahamed *et al.* (2015) determined the size of the female *Puntius sophore* at sexual maturity in the Old Brahmaputra River, North Eastern Bangladesh. Based on the link between standard length and gonadosomatic index, female *P. sophore* was determined to be 4.2 cm standard length at sexual maturity. Relative growth of fork length to standard length, on the other hand, indicated a changeover point at 4 cm standard length, indicating female *P. sophore* size at sexual maturity.

According to Hossain *et al.* (2012) in the Padma River, *Puntius sophore* female size at first maturity was calculated to be 5.00 cm TL. Fecundity was calculated using specimens greater than 5.00 cm TL. Between 1580 to 16590, the mean total fecundity ranged from 5300 to 2700. Total length and total fecundity were found to be positively exponentially correlated ($r^2 = 0.421$). In the Padma River, relative fecundity varied from 466 to 4036 (mean 1100 580).

Langer *et al.* (2013) identified the breeding period of *Puntius sophore* is from July-August. *Puntius sophore* was found to contain oocytes in seven stages. Throughout the entire reproductive cycle, oogonia were present.

Fecundity of *Puntius sophore* was estimated by Kant *et al.* (2016) to be between 1560 and 2314 eggs, with a mean total length of 5.5 cm and a mean body weight of 5.47 gm. The absolute fecundity ranged from 6106.73 to 6942.35 eggs, whereas the relative fecundity varied from 390.85 to 480.18 eggs per fish. Absolute fecundity has a strong ($r^2=0.809$) correlation with ovarian weight but a weak ($r^2=0.047$) and moderate ($r^2=0.216$) correlation with total length and body weight. Therefore, it would seem that ovarian weight had a greater influence on fertility than did body-related factors. A straight-line link between relative and absolute fecundity and body parameters has been found during the current investigations.

Choudhury *et al.* (2015), studied the reproductive features of *Puntius sophore* from the rivers of Tripura, India. Estimated breeding season was July-August. Fecundity was estimated during the peak spawning season (July) and the relative fecundity observed was $4073 \pm 310 \text{ g}^{-1}$ body weight. The average GSI recorded in male and female populations was highest during July month (14.22 ± 3.9 and $20.88 \pm 4.55\%$ respectively)

Hasan *et al.* (2018) identified the breeding season of Pool barb through observation of the gonadosomatic index (GSI), fecundity, oocytes diameter, and gonadal histology of the species. This study compared two populations of Pool barbs (one from Gazipur and the other from Jessore). The highest GSI value was 15.43 ± 2.20 in April at Gazipur, while it was 15.60 ± 1.74 in June at Jessore. The maximum fertility (5053 ± 878.27) was observed in Gazipur in April, while the highest fecundity (5433 ± 968.26) was recorded in Jessore in June. During March, histology of Pool barb's ovary revealed the presence of early and late peri nucleolar stage oocytes, indicating immature oocytes. Pool barb spawning season runs from March to July, with a peak in April to May for the Gazipur region and May to July for the Jessore region, according to histological data. Finally, these findings suggest that breeding season varies from region to region due to environmental and other variables.

2.2 Breeding biology of some other fishes

Mookherjee and Basu (1946) who studied the life history of *Amblypharyngodon mola* was reported that the breeding season of the fish lasted from May to October and a single female can lay 500 eggs at a time.

Qayyum and Qasim (1964) studied the biology of freshwater fishes including *Barbus stigma* from Indian waters and found the ovaries of this fish contained only once during the breeding season.

Karamchandani *et al.* (1967) studied the fecundity of *Tor tor* in India and estimated 43,410 numbers of eggs in a specimen of 750 mm length and also estimated 30,420 eggs from a specimen of 625 mm total length. He reported that the fecundity of *T. tor* would increase with the increase of body length.

Rastogi and Saxena (1968) studied annual changes in the ovarian activity of the cat fish *Mystus tengara* and found nine stages of development showing peak maturation from April to August.

Karim and Hossain (1972) studied the biology of *Mastacembelus pancalus* (Spiny Eel, Hamilton) in artificial ponds. They found the fecundity vary from 1,296 to 3,246 with the mean 2,013. The correlation coefficient of the total length of *M. pancalus* was $r=0.93$. A straight- line regression (Y_e) of fecundity (Y) on weight (X) of ovary of *M. pancalus* was calculated to be $Y_e = 439.19 + 1.786 X$.

Dewan (1973) observed the spawning season of mola to last from April to November in the lake of Bangladesh Agricultural University Campus. The peak period of spawning occurred in August and September. The fecundity of fish ranged from 1,021 to 13,815. The number of eggs increased with the increase in length of the fish.

Malhotra *et al.* (1978) studied ovarian cycle and spawning season of *Ophiocephalus punctatus*, inhabiting Jammu waters, India and reported six well defined stages of maturation and the fish had a prolonged spawning season extending from May to August.

According to Prasad *et al.* (1979) the male and female *Macrognaathus aculeatus* become sexually mature at length of 15.5 cm (about 15 gm) and nearly 18 cm (22 gm) respectively. The fecundity estimated by them was ranging from 210 to 1828.

De-silva and Chandrasoma (1980) studied the reproductive biology of *Sarotherodon mossambicus*, an introduced species, in an ancient a man-made lake in Sri Lanka. The reproductive biology of *Sarotherodon mossambicus* (Peters), a species exotic to Sri Lanka, was established in Parakrama Amudra an ancient man-made lake. Males mature at a length of 27.5 cm and females at a length less than 15 cm. *S. mossambicus* breeds throughout the year with four possible peak periods, which coincide with the tail end of the monsoon and inter monsoon rains. The egg diameter distribution indicates the presence of reserve oocytes and yolked oocytes, the later falling into a single mode between 1.2 to 3.6 mm. Fecundity varied between 360 and 1775 for fish ranging in length from 22 to 31.9 cm and 145 to 538 g in weight.

Mustafa *et al.* (1980) studied on food, feeding habit and fecundity of freshwater Perch *Nandus nandus* (Hamilton), meni fish (Bangladesh). The fecundity ranged between 7,381 eggs for a fish with body length of 9.7 cm and 46,222 eggs for a fish with body length of 13.5 cm. Breeding season ranged from June to July. Mathematical relationship between body length-fecundity and weight-fecundity were found to be linear.

The fecundity *Colisa fasciata* was studied by Banu *et al.* (1984), who mentioned that this fish spawned only at a particular time of the year, i.e., from March to April. The gravid female of this fish contained mature eggs, which ranged from 5,123 to 13,450. Relationship between fecundity and gonad weight was more significant than that between fecundity with others factors.

Mustafa (1991) observed the fecundity and spawning frequency of Kholisa in pond condition and observed that the fecundity of Kholisa was 1,578 to 2,684 with an average of $2,175 \pm 431$. He stated that the species at least two distinct group of eggs in the ovary indicating two breeding seasons.

Kabir *et al.* (1998) determined the fecundity and gonadosomatic index of chapila, *Gudusia chapra* and observed that the male fish attained sexual maturity at 7.7 cm

and 7.14 g and that of the female at 9.3 cm and 14.65 g. The fish was found to spawn for several months with two spawning peaks, one in April and another in August as indicated by the peaks of gonadosomatic index and ova diameter. Fecundity of fish ranged from 25,220 to 154,528 with an average value of 72,328 and was found to increase with the increase in length and weight.

Parween *et al.* (1993) found the breeding season of punti, *Esomus danricus* started in March and continued up to July which a peak in April and May. They also stated that the maximum mean diameter of ova was seen during March to July. The mean diameter of ova in *E. danricus* was found to vary from 0.054 mm (August) to 0.0613 mm (April).

Mamun and Azadi (2003) studied reproductive biology of a fresh water small fish *Salmostoma bacaila* (Hamilton) inhabiting Kaptai reservoir of Bangladesh and found the ripening stages in July, October and February and the fecundity was from 545 (standard length 45 mm and body weight 1200 mg) to 2645 (standard length 90 mm and body weight 4100 mg).

Ziki (2006) studied the reproductive biology of *Mystas vittatus* of a perennial water body in Bangladesh. He suggested that the spawning season of *M. vittatus* were from February to July. Nine stages of oocyte development were observed and indicated that *M. vittatus* was a single spawner, and its spawning frequency or strategy was synchronous type. The minimum standard length (SL) at maturity was 48 mm, and the mean SL at first reproduction estimated from the logistic model was 57.24 mm for females. Fecundity estimates were 4896 to 30215 eggs in terms of standard length. The relations between fecundity (F) and standard length (SL), and between fecundity and body weight (BW) were estimated as $F = 0.1887SL^{2.625}$ ($r^2 = 0.967$) and $F = 1163.9BW + 3680.5$ ($r^2 = 0.992$) respectively.

Ashadullah (2009) studied the reproductive biology of elongated glass perchlet (*Chanda nama*) of the river old Brahmaputra in Bangladesh. He suggested that the range of gonadosomatic index of mature female was from 0.132 to 7.302. Ovarian developments were divided as immature, developing, maturing and spawning

stages on the basis of external features of ovary. Gonadosomatic index, macroscopic appearance of the ovaries suggested that the spawning season of *C. nama* were from February to November. Eight stages of oocyte development were determined and indicated that *C. nama* was a single spawner and its spawning frequency was synchronous type. The minimum standard length at maturity was 28 mm.

Farid (2009) studied the introduction of spawning, larval rearing and culture of tarabaim, *Macrognathus aculeatus* (Bloch). Total length of the sample was ranged from 155.30 ± 3.68 mm to 255.17 ± 3.97 mm, 16.30 ± 1.494 g to 73.67 ± 1.2119 g in weight and fecundity from 1500 ± 449.073 to 5741.67 ± 374.722 eggs. The relationship between fecundity and total length (mm) of fish was found to be expressed as: $Y = 17.77 x + 8017$ ($r^2 = 0.956$). The relationship between fecundity and body weight was found to be expressed as: $Y = 81.086x + 67.816$ ($r^2 = 0.962$).

From the study of Akhter (2011) the experimental fish, giant river catfish, *Sperata seenghala* was collected month-wise (March-August, 2011) from catches of Sylhet basin at the Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University. Routine haematoxylin-eosin (H-E) staining of ovary and observation under microscope revealed oogonia, chromatin nucleolar, perinucleolar, yolk vesicle, early yolk granule, late yolk granule, pre-maturation stage and mature stages of oocytes. Early and developing stage of oocytes were mostly observed during April-May, maturing oocytes in June, and mature oocytes during July-August. Testicular germ cells stages, such as spermatocytes, spermatids, and spermatozoa were observed after H-E staining of testes. Early and developing germ cells were mostly observed during April-May, gradually maturing in June, and mature germ cells during July-August sections of testes.

Motin (2011) studied stages of oocytes and testicular germ cells of endangered pabo catfish (*Ompok pabo*) from the Sylhet basin during the post-spawning season (September to December 2010) at the Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University. Oogonia (o) perinucleolar oocyte (PNO), previtellogenic oocyte (PVO) and yolk granule (YG) stage were observed in developing ovary during the successive month (October to December). It was observed that oocyte did not develop synchronously. In the maturing testes the

testicular germ cell stages of spermatocytes (SPC), spermatids (SPT) and spermatozoa (SPZ) were gradually evident. Empty lumen of tubules (LU) in testes samples during October indicates the peak breeding season just after spent phase.

From the Sylhet basin in the North-East Bangladesh, Alam (2012) studied stages of oocytes of endangered mud eel (*Monopterus albus*) at the Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University. From the histological observation of ovary revealed presence of undeveloped oocyte (UO), oogonium (O), early perinucleolar oocyte (EPNO), late perinucleolar oocyte (LPNO), previtellogenic oocyte (PVO), yolk vesicle (YV), yolk granule (YG), premature (PM) and mature (M) stages of oocytes during samples from March 2011 to February 2012. In this study, the mature stages of oocytes (PM and M oocytes) were found from April to June samples of ovary, indicating the spawning season of *M. albus*. These mature stages occurred high in proportion during late April to mid-May samples indicating peak breeding season of this fish.

Mithu (2012) studied the reproductive physiology and artificial propagation of endangered mud eel (*M. albus*) from the beels of Phulpur upazila under Mymensingh district at the Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University. He found that the highest GSI of $6.002 \pm 1.672\%$ in mid-May and lowest of $0.232 \pm 0.015\%$ in September. This indicated that the peak breeding season of mud eel from late April to early May.

In summary, most of the available studies found on *Puntius sophore* and other species of *Puntius*, the breeding season was commonly at the monsoon, which started from February and extended to the August. The length at maturity was around 50-60 mm. Both cubic and linear relationships were found between length and fecundity, where linear relationships were profound between body weight and fecundity. The reproductive characteristics mainly differed due to variation of the population, habitat, weather-climatic differences.

CHAPTER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Sampling site

3.1.1 Rajdhala Beel, Purbadhala, Netrakona.

Rajdhala Beel is a natural reservoir situated at Purbadhala Upazila in the eastern part of Netrakona district, Bangladesh. It is about 20 km from Netrakona district town. It is a vast wetland covering an area of one hundred and fifty acres.

Due to the clear water and pleasant environment, people who are thirsty for travel come here every day. The huge presence of visitors is raising hopes of tourism potential. Therefore, the locals have demanded infrastructural development.

Figure 2 A view of Rajdhala beel

Figure 3 Map showing the study area

3.1.1.1 Fish samples

Fish samples were collected from the beel monthly and brought to the laboratory for further analysis. Fish samples were collected on monthly basis from July 2020 to June 2021. Water samples were also collected and brought to the laboratory for nutrient analysis.

3.2 Laboratory works

Fish samples were dissected and after dissection of each fish sample several parameters were estimated.

3.2.1 Collection of gonad and sex determination

The abdomens of fishes were cut open by scissors and gonads were collected with forceps carefully. Muscles, fat tissues, digestive organs, blood veins etc. were removed properly. Fishes were sexed as male or female observing the gonad with bare eye. Both left and right gonads were measured together as GW to the nearest 0.0001g. Eventually, these were preserved with 10% formalin in small vials.

3.2.2 Estimation of GSI (Gonadosomatic Index)

The gonadosomatic index (GSI) is often used to follow the reproductive cycle of a species over the year at monthly or less intervals. Gonadosomatic index is define as the percentage of gonad weight to the total body weight of the fish. It is a very powerful method to indicate the spawning season of the species. The gonadosomatic index (GSI) of each fish specimen in the study was determined after measuring gonad weight according to the following formula:

$$\text{GSI} = \frac{\text{Gonad weight}}{\text{Body weight}} \times 100$$

Figure 4 A: An adult female of *Puntius sophore* with isolated matured gonad; B: Taking body weight and gonad weight of samples in laboratory

3.2.3 Observation of ovarian external features

General feature and structure as well as month wise size, shape and colour of female gonads of Pool barb, *Puntius sophore* were studied during sample collection and preservation. External feature of both ovaries was observed by naked eye and microscope at low magnification (x 20). Various developmental stages of ovaries were classified considering their external features and the macroscopic views of eggs. The stages were immature, developing, maturing and spawning.

3.2.4 Histological examination

Conventional histological processing began with preservation of ovaries. Preserved ovaries were trimmed and oriented, dehydrated, infiltrated with paraffin, and formed into blocks of tissue surrounded by supporting medium.

These blocks were then sectioned and slices were mounted on glass slides and stained. Once a cover slip was added, the sections were viewed microscopically. Puncti ovaries were used for histological examination after the following procedure:

1. A transverse segment of about 4 mm thick from the middle part of left ovary was taken.
2. Dehydration of ovarian segment was achieved by the passage of tissue piece through a series of ethyl alcohol solutions in the room temperature according to the following schedule in which a repeated step meant a change of medium.
3. Impregnation of tissue with benzene, a solvent of paraffin was done twice successively for 1 hour each to remove traces of alcohol in order to have consistent paraffin block.
4. Infiltration by melted paraffin at 60 °C was done twice consecutively for a period of 40 minutes each.
5. Following dehydration, cleaning and infiltration by melted paraffin, ovarian segment was placed in a clay mold with melted paraffin for embedment. Care was given to ensure orientation of tissue within the result block, which was allowed to cool within the mold.
6. The paraffin block was cut to serial sections with a thickness of 5 µm each using a microtome and the sections were mounted on clean and adhesive coated slide, the slide was placed in rack within an oven and heated overnight at 200 °C.
7. The slides mounted with gonadal sections were stained by haematoxylin and eosin.
8. Finally, Canada balsam, a mounting medium was applied and cover slip was lowered into place, completely covering the sections.

9. The sections were examined under light microscope ($\times 200$). At least three sections were examined for recording the occurrence of various histological stages of ovary.

3.2.5 Length at sexual maturity

Female classified into various spawning stages by ovarian histology were used to determine minimum length at sexual maturity. For the determination of minimum length at maturity, standard length and GSI values of all female specimens were plotted and female with the lowest standard length having final spawning stage was considered capable of spawning and its standard length was the minimum standard length at maturity of the population.

3.2.6 Estimation of fecundity (F)

Fecundity was estimated using the volumetric method (Diaz *et al.*, 1983). Weight of ovaries were taken using the electronic balance. Portions of ovaries weighed and placed in Gilson's fluid and shaken periodically to release the oocytes. After suspending the oocytes in a volume of (1-1.5 L) water subsamples were taken. In each subsample, oocytes were counted at 50x magnification. The reliability of subsamples tested through analysis of variance (ANOVA) test. The total number of oocytes in the ovaries will be estimated using the following formula:

$$N = \left(\frac{V}{V_1} \right) n \times \left(\frac{W}{W_1} \right)$$

Where, V= Volume of sample, V_1 = Volume of subsample, W= Weight of ovary, W_1 = Weight of portion of ovary, n is the number of oocytes in the sub-sample.

There are several methods for the estimation of fecundity of fish of which are actual counting method was found to be the most accurate one. But this method is very tedious and time consuming and to certain extent rather impossible in case of high fecund fishes. When the actual counting of eggs is impracticable, approximate fecundity may be obtained by one of the following methods as outlined by (Lagler, 1952).

- a) Volumetric method
- b) Gravimetric method
- c) Von Vayer method

Volumetric method and Von vayer method have been found to be suitable for relatively large eggs. But the eggs of *P. sophore* are comparatively smaller and which may lead to error in the estimation of fecundity by Von vayer method and volumetric method. Gravimetric method was found to be more efficient than those of other methods and gave fairly accurate results. The gravimetric or weight method has been successfully used by Doha and Hye (1970), Shafi and Quddus (1974) etc. Therefore, gravimetric method was thought, may offer the best possibility of minimizing error due to its simple and easy sampling technique.

Fecundity is defined as the number of oocytes shed by a female in a spawning season was estimated gravimetrically. In this method, prior to estimation, oocytes from samples (0.0001 g) obtained from three portions (anterior, middle and posterior) of five ovarian lobes randomly were counted and measured to determine whether they had significance differences between locations. Results showed that oocytes were uniformly distributed, and in the succeeding analysis, sample was taken from the middle portion. A section of about 4 mm long was cut from middle part of the right ovary, weighted to nearest 0.0001 g (gw) after removal of formalin from the ovary surface with tissue paper, and put into a Petri dish with a small amount of water. All the eggs were separated from each other with needles and measured along their longest axis under stereomicroscope. A frequency distribution of egg size by 1 μ interval was constructed, the number of eggs in the largest modal group, b, was summed. Fecundity, F was calculated using the following formula:

$$F = B \times \frac{GW}{gw}$$

Where,

F = Fecundity of fish, GW = Gonad weight, B = Number of eggs in sample and

gw = Sample weight

3.2.7 Gonad histology

To get solid evidence of the findings, histology of female gonads was done to determine the gonadal development. Histology process was done at Ecophysiology

Laboratory, Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University.

3.2.7.1 Process of gonad histology:

Histological processes were undertaken at the Fish Ecophysiology Laboratory, Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University. The gonad of each fish was preserved in 10% buffered formalin with labeled vials for further study. The preserved samples after cutting into square size were taken out in a perforated plastic holder, which was covered by perforated steel plates. Cleaning, infiltration and dehydration process will be carried out in an automatic tissue processor using a series of alcohol of increasing concentrations, two changes of xylene and finally through molten wax (three series) as mentioned in Table 1 Time schedule in the automatic tissue processor

Paraffin embedded blocks were cut by microtome knife at 4-5 μm size and left the sections into a water bath at a temperature of 40 °C. The sections were placed on a glass slide and kept overnight on a slide drier hot plate at a temperature of 20 °C. Then the sections were stained routinely with haematoxylin and eosin (Humason, 1962) as per the schedule given in Table 2. The consecutive steps of conducting histology of gonad of *P. sophore* are demonstrated in Figure 5.

Table 1 Time schedule in the automatic tissue processor

Sl. No.	Steps of process	Time (hour)	Process
1	50% Methylated spirit	1	
2	80% Methylated spirit	2	
3	100% Methylated spirit	2	
4	100% Methylated spirit	2	Dehydration
5	100% Methylated spirit	2	
6	100% Alcohol	2	
7	100% Alcohol	2	
8	Xylene	2	
9	Xylene	1	
10	Molten wax	1	Infiltration
11	Molten wax	2	
12	Molten wax	2	
	Total	21	

Table 2 Staining procedure for histological study of gonad

Sl. No.	Staining process	Solution	Times (min)
1	Clearing	Xylene	3
2		Xylene	3
3	Rehydration	100% Alcohol	2
4		100% Alcohol	2
5		95% Alcohol	2
6		870% Alcohol	2
7	Running tap water		5
8	Staining	Haematoxylin	1 dip
9	Running tap water		25
10	Counter stain	Eosin	1
11	Dehydration	70% Alcohol	1
12		95% Alcohol	2
13		100% Alcohol	2
14		100% Alcohol	2
15	Clearing	Xylene	2
16		Xylene	2

Figure 5 Flow chart showing histology processes of gonad

3.3 Data analysis

Microsoft Excel 2019 (Microsoft Corporation, 2020) was used to tabulate the raw data and analysed using the R programming language (R Core Team, 2021). The analyses were done using R-Studio (RStudio Team, 2022), and ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016) package was used to make graphs and charts. A one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variances) was performed to determine whether there were significant differences in body indices between months. The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was utilized to determine the differences (Duncan, 1955).

The models of regression regarding different relationships were compared and the best model were selected for measuring the dependencies of fecundity. The relationships between bodyweight and standard length were measured and related analysis were done in R-studio IDE. R-scrips of data analysis has been provided into the Appendix -2.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

4.1 Fish size

4.1.1 Standard length of fishes

Standard length of collected fishes ranged from 49 to 96 mm over the study period (Table 3 and Figure 6). Fish specimens collected on June 2021 were largest ($P < 0.01$) in size in terms of standard length ranging from 58-87 mm and 61.00-96.00 mm respectively. Fish samples caught on March 2021, April 2021, May 2021 and July 2020 were medium in terms of standard length varied from 56.00-72.10 mm, 56-82 mm, 58 - 87 mm and 55 - 82 mm respectively. On other months, standard length ranged from 52.50-59.00 mm in January-2021, 49.30-61.50 mm in August, 50.80-60.60 mm in September 2020, 50.60-78.00 mm in October 2020, and 49-70 mm in December 2021 which were statistically smallest ($P < 0.01$) throughout the study period.

Table 3 Standard length (mm) of monthly collected specimens (July 2020- June 2021)

Months	Min. SL	Max. SL	Mean SL	SD	No of female fish	F value	LSD (5%)
Jan	52.50	59.00	55.64 ^d	0.16	20		
Feb	50.80	66.00	57.94 ^{cd}	0.46	20		
Mar	56.00	72.10	66.59 ^b	0.47	22		
Apr	56.00	82.00	69.38 ^b	0.77	13		
May	58.00	87.00	66.33 ^b	0.69	24		
Jun	61.00	96.00	83.18^a	0.79	28	42.454	4.95
Jul	55.00	82.00	65.10 ^b	0.76	21		
Aug	49.30	61.50	55.24 ^d	0.34	22		
Sep	50.80	60.60	55.12 ^d	0.27	20		
Oct	50.60	78.00	55.62 ^d	0.66	15		
Nov	51.07	77.00	60.59 ^c	0.91	20		
Dec	49.00	70.00	57.45 ^{cd}	0.56	20		

SL: Standard Length; SD: Standard Deviation; LSD: Least significant difference; In a column figure with same letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT).

Figure 6 Frequency distributions of standard length of *P. sophore*

4.1.2 Body weight of fishes

During the sampling period, the body weight of fish specimens captured ranged from 3.8-19.5 g (Table 4 and Figure 7). Specimens caught in August 2020, September 2020, October 2020 and December 2020 had the lowest average body weight with one percent level of significance ($P < 0.01$) (Table 4). Fish samples collected in November 2020, February 2021 and March 2021 comprised medium weight ranging from 4.59-10 g, 5.37-8.66 g and 5.35-9.19 g respectively, though there were some large and small fish but these were few in number. Fish sample collected on July 2020, April 2021, May 2021, June 2021 and were large in weight which range varied from 4.6-15.75 g, 5.84-15 g, 6.34-17 g and 7.65-19.50 g respectively. Among the specimens with high body weight specimens from June 2020 were statistically higher than all other months ($p < 0.01$).

Table 4 Body weight (g) of monthly samples specimens (July 2020-June 2021)

Months	Min. BW	Max. BW	Mean BW	SD	No of samples	F value	LSD (5%)
Jan	5.07	6.43	5.89 ^{de}	0.34	20	48.268	1.73
Feb	5.37	8.66	6.54 ^{cde}	0.94	20		
Mar	5.35	9.19	7.51 ^c	1.18	22		
Apr	5.84	15.00	9.74 ^b	3.15	13		
May	6.34	17.00	10.06 ^b	2.92	24		
Jun	7.65	19.50	15.77 ^a	3.14	28		
Jul	4.66	15.75	9.00 ^b	3.10	21		
Aug	4.48	6.32	5.74 ^{de}	0.62	22		
Sep	4.00	7.30	6.03 ^{de}	0.72	20		
Oct	4.65	9.95	5.83 ^{de}	1.20	15		
Nov	4.59	10.00	7.17 ^{cd}	2.27	20		
Dec	3.84	9.00	5.50 ^e	1.37	20		

BW: Body Weight; SD: Standard Deviation; LSD: Least significant difference; In a column figure with same letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT).

Figure 7 Frequency distributions of body weight of *P. sophore*

4.2 Determination of breeding season

The month-wise gonadosomatic index, external features, fecundity of *P. sophore* were determined and established the relationship between standard length-fecundity, body weight-fecundity to study the reproductive biology of this species. Ovarian developments were observed to determine the breeding season.

4.2.1 Gonadosomatic index (GSI) method

The gonadosomatic index, the indicator of the status of gonadal development and maturity of individuals of experimental species, was calculated for fish *P. sophore* during July 2020 to June 2021. The frequency distributions and the values of gonadosomatic index of fish are shown in Figure 8, and Table 5.

Figure 8 Frequency distributions of gonadosomatic index of *P. sophore*

The GSI values in the month of March, April, May, June and July were ranged from 4.63-14.45, 8.12-13.57, 8.78-18.10, 12.50-17.17, and 8.8-12.64 respectively. From August 2020 to February 2021, there was very small GSI values varied from 1.78-4.03, 0.23-4.27, 1.88-4.42, 0.34-0.82, 0.08-0.74, 0.37-0.82, and 0.37-0.82 respectively. Only in March the GSI value was medium.

Indicatively, the GSI of fish started to increase in March, gradually peaked in May and June then steadily declined in August. After that GSI declined sharply in August to February. The GSI values for female showed one peaks from March to July. Statistically highest GSI was observed in May 2021 and June 2021 ($p < 0.01$) and decreased as spawning progressed (Figure 9).

These data suggest that one breeding season might occur starting from March to July.

Table 5 Month-wise gonadosomatic index of *P. sophore* (July 2020-June 2021)

Months	Min.	Max.	Mean.	SD	No. of fish	F value	LSD (5%)
Jan	0.37	0.82	0.64 ^f	0.13	20		
Feb	0.37	0.82	0.61 ^f	0.14	20		
Mar	4.63	14.45	9.87^c	2.05	22		
Apr	8.12	13.57	11.31^b	1.86	13		
May	8.78	18.10	13.18^a	2.17	24		
Jun	12.50	17.17	14.24^a	1.10	28		
Jul	8.8	12.64	9.33^d	1.41	21	236.455	1.06
Aug	1.78	4.03	2.88 ^e	0.57	22		
Sep	0.23	4.27	2.62 ^e	0.76	20		
Oct	1.88	4.42	3.14 ^e	0.90	15		
Nov	0.34	0.82	0.63 ^f	0.16	20		
Dec	0.08	0.74	0.49 ^f	0.21	20		

SD: Standard Deviation; LSD: Least significant difference;

In a column figure with same letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT).

Figure 9 Monthly changes of gonadosomatic index of *P. sophore* (July 2019-June 2021)

4.2.2 External feature of ovary

A total 245 of fish (44.9 - 96 mm standard length) were collected from July 2020 to June 2021 and external feature of all ovaries were examined by naked eye and under microscope of low magnification (x 20).

4.2.2.1 Ovarian macroscopic stages and their characteristics

Ovaries were classified into 4 maturity stages based on external features of gonads and the appearance of oocytes. The stages were characterized as:

- **Immature (Stage I):** Young fish that had small white translucent ovaries and they were thin and translucent. No eggs were observed by naked eye.
- **Developing (Stage II):** The gonad grew quickly in terms of weight. Colour began to change in pinkish and orange in some specimens or dark yellow in other. Ovary was about one-third of the body cavity. Oocytes were opaque granule observed as rounded cells of different sizes.
- **Maturing (Stage III):** Gonads changed to more intensive colour (Figure 10). Ovaries were turgid and occupied two-third of the body cavity. Eggs were observed by naked eye as spherical opaque granules, translucent and large.

- **Spawning (Stage IV):** Sexual products were mature. Gonads reached its maximum weight. Colour was little bit darker and eggs were abundant, big, transparent and free in ovary.

Figure 10 Matured ovary of *Puntius sophore*

4.2.2.2 Frequency occurrence of ovarian stages

Monthly changes in the occurrence of ovarian developmental stages are shown in Figure 11. For ovarian development, immature ovaries were found least in the month of May and June. Developing ovaries were observed in every month with different percentages and with the highest percentages (51%) in March 2021. Maturing (ripe) ovaries were found in seven months from February 2021 to September 2020, with the highest percentage (22%) in April 2021. Spawning ovaries were observed from April to July, with the highest percentage (75%) in June 2021.

Female having ovaries at spawning stages were considered those spawning or near to spawn. The occurrence of spawning ovaries began to appear in April and continued up to July. Percent occurrence of spawning ovaries started to increase in April and gradually peaked in June.

No ovaries with spawning stage were found in August. After that it was not found in August to February. Examination of external characteristics of ovaries suggested that *Puntius sophore* spawned once in a year, i.e., from March to July.

Figure 11 Monthly changes in the frequency of the occurrence of ovarian maturity

4.2.3 Histology of ovary

A total of 245 ovaries (49-50 mm SL) were sectioned histologically. Ten ovaries were chosen randomly from each sampling throughout the study period.

4.2.3.1 Maturity stages and their histological characteristics

According to the histological observation of ovaries in *P. sophore*, the maturity stages were as follows:

- I. **Early perinucleolus stage (EP):** Oocytes had cytoplasm and nucleoli, which stained deeply with haematoxylin (basophilic). Nucleus was not basophilic. Several peripheral nucleoli were seen in the inner surface of the nucleus (Figure 12-A).
- II. **Yolk vesicle stage (YV):** Oocytes became bigger and less basophilic but still stained with haematoxylin. White yolk vesicles started to appear initially in the outer part of cytoplasm, but gradually increasing in size and number situated randomly in the cytoplasm, in the middle part or surrounding the nucleus (Figure 12-B).
- III. **Primary yolk stage (PY):** Small and spherical yolk globule began to appear among yolk vesicles in the peripheral region of cytoplasm (Figure 12-C).

- IV. **Migratory nucleus stage (MN):** Nucleus progressively migrated towards the animal pole of the oocyte, due to the resumption of the meiosis. Oil droplets situated in the inner part of the cytoplasm. Yolk globules started to fuse one to each other too, being gradually bigger and less acidophilic (Figure 12-D).
- V. **Premature stage (PM):** After the nucleus migration, nuclear membrane broke down (germinal vesicle breakdown). Yolk globules coalesced and no nucleus was observed, although the follicle layer was still visible (Figure 12-D).

Figure 12 Maturity stages from histology of *P. shopore's* gonad

4.2.3.2 Frequency occurrence of maturity stages of oocytes

Figure 13 Frequency occurrence of maturity stages of oocytes

Figure 13 shows the frequency (%) occurrence of five maturity stage of 245 females during the study period. In November 2020, 100% of female oocytes were in the early perinucleolus stage. In December, 70% were in the early perinucleolus, 30% were yolk vesicle stage. In January 2021, early perinucleolus were 50%, yolk vesicle was 40% and rest were primary yolk. In February 2021, 20% of female oocytes were in early perinucleolus stage, 60% were in yolk vesicle and rest 20% were primary

yolk. In March 2021, of 10 specimens of 30% were early perinucleolus, 20% were yolk vesicle and 50% were primary yolk. In April 2021, only 20% were early perinucleolus, yolk vesicles were 10%, and primary yolk contained equal percentages of early perinucleolus, 30% of migratory nucleus and rest of 20% were premature stages. In May 2021, only 10% were early perinucleolus and of 20% were primary yolk, migratory nucleus was of 20% and rest 50% were premature stages. In June, 90% were premature stages only 10% were migratory nucleus stage.

In July, 80% were early perinucleolus and rest of 20% was yolk vesicle and no premature stages were observed. In August, 70% were early perinucleolus, yolk vesicle was 20%, primary yolk comprised 10%. In September, 70% were early perinucleolus, 20% were comprised of yolk vesicle and only 10% were primary yolk. In October, of 90% were early perinucleolus and only 10% were yolk vesicle stages.

Early perinucleolus oocytes were found throughout the year except June with the highest percentage in November. Yolk vesicle oocytes were observed December to October except May and June with highest percentage in February. Primary yolk globules started to appear from August to September. This stage was also observed in the month of January to May. Migratory nucleolus oocytes were observed in April to June with the highest percentage in April. The premature oocytes appeared in the month of April to June.

The premature stage was observed as the most advanced mature stage in this study. The most advanced premature stage oocyte i.e., premature oocyte was present from April to June and maintaining high value in the month of June with 90%. There was no premature oocyte observed in the month of July. Then it occurred in the month of April to some extent and gradually peak in the month of June. These results indicated one spawning season of *Puntius sophore* precisely lasted from April to June.

Figure 13 Frequency occurrence of maturity stages of oocytes

4.3 Frequency of spawning and measurement of egg diameter

For the measurement of egg diameter about 100 eggs were taken randomly from the mixed sample of eggs for mature fish species. These were arranged in several rows on a glass slide and diameter of individual ova was taken with the help of stereomicroscope. The diameter of ova along whatever axis they lay parallel to the graduation of the micrometre, were measured to ensure random nature of the readings and unbiased values as suggested by Clark (1934). The measurements of egg diameter were taken in millimetre along the longest axis of the egg. Frequency distributions of egg diameter of ovaries were ranged from 0.4 mm to 0.8 mm in size and fecundity were counted as from 0.6 mm to 0.8 mm. The size range of 0.4 mm were not included as fecundity estimation because of their very smaller in size (Figure 18). The above facts concluded that *Puntius sophore* was a single spawner, i.e., synchronous species and it spawned once in a spawning season.

Figure 14 Size frequency distribution of oocytes of *P. sophore*

4.4 Minimum length at maturity

Female ovaries classified to premature stages were used to determine the minimum length at maturity. Female having premature oocyte was in standard length of 56 mm and its gonadosomatic index was 7.48. The relationship between gonadosomatic index (GSI) and standard length (SL) of female having mature gonad has been demonstrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Relationship between gonadosomatic index (GSI) and standard length of female having mature gonad. Yellow dot indicates the GSI of youngest adult female having 56 mm SL in this study

4.5 Fecundity

After estimating the breeding season, depending on the egg diameter 133 female specimens were taken for fecundity estimation. The range of relative fecundity was from 450 to 4352 per gm of mature female in terms of standard length from 56 mm to 92 mm respectively (Table 6).

Table 6 Monthly fecundity of *P. sophore*

Months	Mean fecundity	Min. of fecundity	Max. of fecundity	No of Fish examined	F-value	LSD (5%)
Mar- 21	1713.129 ^c	520	2315	22		
Apr- 21	1827.909 ^c	720	2781	11		
May-21	2284.833 ^b	1440	4005	12		
Jun-21	3358.654 ^a	1494	4352	26	65.904	386.76
Jul-20	1546.35 ^c	520	2621	20		
Aug-20	1262 ^d	998	1478	22		
Sep-20	1092.85 ^d	816	1500	20		

LSD: Least significant difference

In a column figure with same letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT).

4.5.1 Relationship between fecundity and standard length

The scatter diagram obtained from the fecundity and standard length showed a non-linear cubic relationship (Figure 16). In the determination of this relation, standard length was taken as independent variable, while fecundity as dependent variable. Standard length and fecundity yielded cubic relationship, the equation was $F = 0.0232SL^{2.6877}$ ($r^2=0.8683$) and the yielded equation indicated that fecundity was highly correlated with the standard length of fish.

Figure 16 The relationship between fecundity and standard length of *P. sophore* during spawning season

4.5.2 Relation between fecundity and body weight

The scatter diagrams obtained from the fecundity and body weight showed a linear relationship (Figure 17). In the determination of this relation, body weight was taken as independent variant, while fecundity as dependent variant. The relationship between fecundity and body weight was in the form of straight line, and the estimated equation was $F = 213.44BW + 125.24$ ($r^2 = 0.892$) and it was concluded that fecundity was highly correlated with the body weight of fish.

Figure 18 shows the frequency distribution of egg diameters of the experimental units and the diameter of egg from where fecundity counting was started.

Figure 17 The relationship between fecundity and body weight of *P. sophore* during spawning season

Figure 18 Size frequency distribution of oocytes of *P. sophore*. Fecundity was counted with the eggs right to the arrow

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

The knowledge on reproductive biology of fish is essential for evaluating the commercial potentialities of its stock, life history, culture practice and management of its fishery. In order to achieve success in fish culture it is important to assess the yearly breeding cycle of culturable fishes. Some of them breed once a year while some at regular intervals throughout the year. Information of gonadal development and the spawning season of a species is also important for its management.

The aim of the study of reproductive biology of Pool barb, *P. sophore* was to identify the spawning seasons, determine the minimum length at maturity, frequency of spawning, maturation stages of oocytes, frequency distribution of eggs and fecundity of the species. Therefore, the investigation was carried out from July 2020 to June 2021 in a natural reservoir of the Rajdhala beel, Purbadhala, Netrokona, Bangladesh.

The gonadosomatic index (GSI), which is indicative of the breeding season of the fish, had been calculated from March to June. There was a sudden rise in the values in March and gradually increased till June. The highest gonadosomatic index of *P. sophore* was in June and the lowest was in December. This indicates that *P. sophore* may breed in March to June. These data suggest that one spawning season might occur from March to July. These findings agree with the findings of Mitra *et al.* (2005) and Hasan *et al.* (2018).

Alam *et al.* (2014) found the breeding season of pool barb from May to August while Bithy *et al.* (2013) reported the months from June to August. Bithy *et al.* (2013) also determined July as a breeding month of *P. sophore*. Moreover, Mitra *et al.* (2005) observed that the breeding season of this fish extended February to August and May-June as spawning months.

Hasan *et al.* (2018) found that the breeding season runs from March to July, peaking in April and May in Gazipur Bangladesh. The same study also identified May to July as the breeding season in Jessore, Bangladesh. Due to the fact that Jessore is a

baor area with numerous baors and beels, the current study location Rajdhala beel has similar hydrographic characteristics, which could be one explanation for the parallels between the two studies.

Peaks of the GSI index value in June might be due to completion of maturity and subsequent steep fall in the index value clearly indicated alternatively the spawning and spent condition of fish. The gonadosomatic index increased with the maturation of fish, being maximum during the period of peak maturity and declined abruptly thereafter, when fish became spent (LeCren, 1951). Treasurer and Holiday (1981) in studies with *Perca fluviatilis*, Piska *et al.* (1991) with *Salmostona phulo* stated that GSI was useful for establishing spawning period. The monthly changes in GSI reflect the ovarian activity of fish and it must be noticed that GSI is a reliable tool to determine peak spawning season (Vladimir, 2000). However, the present results were fully agreed with that of Mitra *et al.* (2005). Additionally, the occurrence of spawning ovaries examined by external characteristics began to appear in March and continued up to July. Percent occurrence of ovaries started to increase in March and peaked in June. It appeared in March to some extent and gradually peaked in June and steadily declined in August. After that it was not found in September to February.

In the present study, monthly changes of gonadosomatic index for *P. sophore* revealed that mean GSI increased once in a year in June suggested one peaks of GSI. Various developmental stages of ovaries were classified considering their external features and the macroscopic views of eggs. The stages were immature, developing, maturing and spawning. External morphology and macroscopic observation of female gonads showed that the spawning season of pool barb was March to July. This finding is similar to findings of Mitra *et al.* (2005); Bithy *et al.* (2013) and Alam *et al.* (2014) who found one peak breeding season for *P. sophore* in different regions. Alam *et al.* (2014) found the season to be May to August in Bangladesh while Bithy *et al.* (2013) reported the season to be June to August with July as peak month in Bangladesh. These results are similar to the finding of this study, where March to July is the breeding period of Pool barb in Rajdhala beel in Netrakona, Bangladesh.

Histology is a powerful tool for biological assessment. In this study, oocytes maturity stages were classified into five stages as early perinucleolus stage, yolk vesicle stage, primary yolk stage, migratory nucleus stage and premature stage.

The premature stage was observed as the most advanced stage in the study. Most advanced mature stages indicated that probability of spawning might be occurred within short time. Other advanced maturity stages were not found surely because the sampling time was during the morning, when ovaries might not supposed to be ready for ovulation and spawn yet. It is believed that if samples are taken in late afternoon and evening during the spawning season, more advanced maturity stages may appear (Vladimir, 2000). However, females classified into premature stage were supposed to ready for capable of spawning or near to spawn. The most advanced premature stage oocyte i.e., premature oocyte was present from March to June. There was no premature oocyte observed in the month of September. These results indicated one spawning season of *P. sophore* precisely lasted from March to June. Ovary of *P. sophore* was a synchronous type that contained almost similar oocyte maturation stages.

This type of oocyte maturity was by far the most common strategy among teleost (Wallace and Selmann, 1981; Lee *et al.*, 2005) studied with *Leiognathus equulus* and found eight maturity stages of oocytes as chromatin nucleolus, perinucleolus, yolk vesicle, primary yolk, secondary yolk, tertiary yolk, migratory nucleus and ripe stage by histological examination of ovaries.

Spawning frequency may be determined on the basis of the occurrence or presence of postovulatory follicle, hydrated eggs (De Martini and Fountain, 1981; Hunter and Macewicz, 1985) and mode of frequency distribution of egg diameter (Sherry *et al.*, 1996). In fact, hydrated eggs and postovulatory follicles were not observed in the ovaries throughout the study period.

The presence of almost same oocyte maturity stages in the histological section of matured female ovaries were observed during the study period which indicated that female *P. sophore* were single spawner (i.e., may spawn only once during a single spawning season). While in case of multiple or serial spawner, fish may

spawn more than once during a single spawning season. Post ovulatory follicles or hydrated eggs are the indications of a serial spawner (George, 1996). But no postovulatory follicles or hydrated eggs were found in the current study. Hence, this information revealed that the experimental fish spawned once in a spawning season.

The study found that the standard length of the youngest female that bore mature eggs was 56 mm, and its gonadosomatic index was 7.48. Minimum size of maturity is not an independent criterion, but is one that closely associated with the other features of growth, food supply, etc. of a particular stock or population. In general, minimum size of maturity is also related to the longevity and the rate of growth. When the sexes differ in longevity that with the lower longevity tends to have a higher rate of growth and minimum size of maturity and vice versa. In the west coast spart the growth rate and longevity of the sexes have been shown to be almost identical (De-Silva, 1973) and hence, as expected, both sexes have the same minimum size and age at maturation. This finding is similar to the findings of Hossain *et al.* (2012) and Mitra *et al.* (2005).

The range of relative fecundity was from 540 to 4352 per gm of mature female which maintained standard length from 56 mm to 92 mm. It was observed that female specimens belonging to the same size group had different number of eggs in their ovaries. Lagler *et al.* (1967) reported that the number of eggs produced by an individual female was dependent on various factors like size, age, condition and type of species of the fish. It was also observed in some cases that the fecundity of some larger fishes was much less than that of some smaller fishes. This type of variation was also reported by different workers (Doha and Hye, 1970; Karim and Hossain, 1972). The relationship between the fecundity and standard length of *P. sophore* found to be nonlinear cubic relation and was expressed as $F = 0.0232SL^{2.6877}$ ($r^2=0.8683$) during spawning season (i.e., from March to July). The equation yielded $r^2=0.8683$ indicated that fecundity was highly correlated with the standard length of fish. Similar relationship for *P. sophore* was found by Tareque *et al.* (2008). Some other studies found linear relationship between fecundity and length of *P. sophore* (Bithy *et al.*, 2013; Srivastava, 2003; Kant *et al.*, 2016).

The relationship between the fecundity and body weight of *P. sophore* was linear and it was expressed as $F = 213.44BW + 125.24$ ($r^2 = 0.892$) during spawning season. From the linear value $r^2=0.892$, it was concluded that fecundity was highly correlated with the body weight of fish which is related to the findings of Srivastava (2003); Tareque *et al.* (2008); Bithy *et al.* (2013) and Kant *et al.* (2016).

The findings of this study can be said reliable as all the findings were more or less matches with the related literatures and findings. Most of the dissimilarities occurred due to variation of regional and environmental factors.

CHAPTER 6

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present experiment was designed to study the reproductive biology of Pool barb Punti (*Puntius sophore*) in Rajdhala beel, Netrakona. The aim of the study of reproductive biology of Pool barb, *P. sophore* was to identify the breeding season, minimum length at maturity, frequency of spawning, maturation stages of oocytes, frequency distribution of eggs and fecundity of the species. For this purposes month wise gonadosomatic index, external features of ovary, gonadal maturity, gonadal histology and fecundity of *P. sophore* were determined and established the relationship between standard length-fecundity, and body weight-fecundity of this species.

Samples of *P. sophore* were collected from the Rajdhala beel, Purbadhala, Netrokona, Bangladesh from July 2020 to June 2021. The fish specimens were collected monthly using seine net having small meshes. Three methods were employed to determine the breeding season. Monthly mean gonadosomatic index was found highest in June. Since mean gonadosomatic index was highest in June, and after that started to decline therefore it was opined that the spawning took place after June apparently.

Very few studies on biology of pool barb, *P. sophore* have been made in several water bodies though it is one of the most important small indigenous fishes in Bangladesh. The study was conducted to obtain the fundamental knowledge on reproductive parameters of the fish that was essential for evaluating the commercial potentialities of its stock, life history, culture practice and management.

The highest GSI value of *P. sophore* were obtained from March to July which increased from March and gradually peaked in June. Then it declined sharply in July and it was not appeared from September to February. These data suggest that only one spawning season might occur; i.e., from March to July.

Various developmental stages of ovaries were classified considering their external features and the macroscopic views of eggs. The stages were immature, developing,

maturing and spawning. External morphology and macroscopic observation of female gonads showed that the spawning season of Pool barb was from March to July.

The microscopic examinations of gonad histology detected the presence of five maturity stages of oocyte which were early perinucleolus, yolk vesicle stage, primary yolk stage, migratory nucleus stage and premature stage. Monthly plotting of percent data of histological stages revealed that the most advanced stage detected in this study occurred in April, May and June. Based on histological investigation it was eventually concluded that the spawning season of *P. sophore* existed from April to July. Postovulatory follicles and hydrated eggs were absent in the mature ovaries over the study period which gave the support that *P. sophore* was a synchronous single spawner.

The study found that the standard length of the youngest female that bore mature eggs was 56 mm, and its gonadosomatic index was 7.48 and the egg diameter which was counted for fecundity was ranged from 0.5-0.9 mm. The range of relative fecundity was from 520 to 4352 per gm of mature female which maintained standard length from 56 mm to 92 mm. Standard length and fecundity yielded cubic relationship, the equation was $F = 0.0232SL^{2.6877}$ ($r^2=0.8683$). The relationship between fecundity and body weight was in the form of a straight line, and the estimated equation was $F=213.44BW+125.24$ ($r^2=0.892$).

Finally, as an important indigenous species pool barb required extensive conservation schemes in different waterbodies as it is self-recruiting species. Outcomes of this study may help the researchers in further analysis of population dynamics of pool barb in Rajdhala beel. To get evidence about the outcome of this study, further investigation on recruitment and other population parameters are required. The present study was concluded that the relationships between fecundity and standard length of fishes were found to be cubic and highly significant, and the relationship between fecundity and body weight of fishes were found to be linear and highly significant.

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APPENDICES

Appendix- 1 Analysis of Variance (One-way ANOVA) of monthly standard length (SL), body weight (BW), gonadosomatic index and fecundity

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
SL(cm)	Between Groups	184.153	11	16.741	42.454	<0.001
	Within Groups	91.882	233	.394		
	Total	276.035	244			
BW (g)	Between Groups	2377.303	11	216.118	48.268	<0.001
	Within Groups	1043.257	233	4.477		
	Total	3420.560	244			

GSI

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		5635.013	11	512.274	236.455	<0.001
Within Groups		418.130	193	2.166		
Total		6053.143	204			

Fecundity

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		90681264.315	6	15113544.052	65.904	<0.001
Within Groups		28895369.363	126	229328.328		
Total		119576633.678	132			

DATA ANALYSIS FOR REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY OF PUNTI (*P. SOPHORE*) IN RAJHDHALA RESERVOIR, NETROKONA

Md. Ashfaq Sadat

Loading Data from Raw data

```
library(readr)
data_punti <- read_csv("data_punti.csv",
  col_types = cols(Month_NO = col_factor(levels = c("1",
    "2", "3", "4", "5", "6", "7", "8",
    "9", "10", "11", "12")), Sex = col_skip(), Month = col_factor(le
    vels = c("January", "February", "March", "April", "May", "June", "July",
    "August", "September", "October", "November", "December"))))

# Loading monthly Gonadal Stage Frequency Data

gonadFreq <- read_csv("Frequency of Gonad Stages.csv",
  col_types = cols(Month = col_factor(levels = c("January", "February",
    "March", "April", "May", "June", "July", "August", "September", "October"
    , "November", "December")), Stages = col_factor(levels = c("Resting",
    "Developing", "Ripe", "Spawning",
    "Spent")), Percent = col_integer()))

## Warning: One or more parsing issues, see `problems()` for details

# Loading monthly histology Frequency Data
histFreq <- read_csv("histFreq.csv",
  col_types = cols(month = col_factor(levels = c("January", "February",
    "March", "April", "May", "June", "July", "August", "September", "October"
    , "November", "December")), stages = col_factor(levels = c("EP",
    "YV", "PY", "MN",
    "PM")), percent = col_integer()))
```

Distribution of Total length along months

```
library(ggplot2)
ggplot(data=data_punti, aes(SL_mm)) + geom_histogram(bins=5)+facet_wrap(
  data_punti$Month)+ylab("Frequency")+xlab("Standard Length (mm)")
```


Distribution of Body Weight along months

```
library(ggplot2)
ggplot(data=data_punti, aes(BW)) + geom_histogram(bins = 5)+facet_wrap(d
ata_punti$Month)+ylab("Frequency")+xlab("Body Weight (g)")
```


Distribution of GSI along months

```
library(ggplot2)
ggplot(data=data_punti, aes(GSI)) + geom_histogram(bins=6)+facet_wrap(da
ta_punti$Month)+ylab("Frequency")+xlab("Gonadosomatic Index")
## Warning: Removed 40 rows containing non-finite values (stat_bin).
```



```
library(ggplot2)
ggplot(data=data_punti, aes(Diameter)) + geom_histogram(bins = 7, boundary = 0)+ylab("Frequency")+xlab("Egg Diameter")
## Warning: Removed 118 rows containing non-finite values (stat_bin).
```


Monthly Changes in Gonadosomatic index

Frequency of Gonadal Development

```
ggplot(gonadFreq, aes(x=Month, y = Percent, fill= Stages))+geom_col()+guides(fill=guide_legend(reverse=FALSE))+
```

```

theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))+labs(x = "Months",
", y = "Frequency Percent (%)")
## Warning: Removed 16 rows containing missing values (position_stack).

```


Frequency of Histology Development

```

ggplot(histFreq,aes(x=month, y = percent, fill= stages))+geom_col()+guid
es(fill=guide_legend(reverse=TRUE))+
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))+labs(x = "Months",
", y = "Frequency Percent (%)")
## Warning: Removed 27 rows containing missing values (position_stack).

```


Models

```
data_punti%>%
  filter(!is.na(Fecundity)) -> df
#
sl_model <- lm(log(df$Fecundity) ~ log(df$SL_mm))
summary(sl_model)

##
## Call:
## lm(formula = log(df$Fecundity) ~ log(df$SL_mm))
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -0.78290 -0.13309  0.00608  0.14184  0.51336
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   -3.8297      0.4827  -7.934 8.29e-13 ***
## log(df$SL_mm)  2.6877      0.1153  23.318 < 2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 0.2228 on 131 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.8059, Adjusted R-squared:  0.8044
## F-statistic: 543.8 on 1 and 131 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16

coef(sl_model)

##      (Intercept) log(df$SL_mm)
##      -3.829672      2.687672

# The overall F-value of the model is 511.2 and the corresponding p-value
# is extremely small (< 2.2e-16), which indicates that the model as a whole
# is useful.
#
# Using the coefficients from the output table, we can see that the fitted
# power regression equation is:
#
#  $\ln(F) = -3.7614 + 2.6718 \cdot \ln(SL)$ 
#
# Applying exp to both sides, we can rewrite the equation as:
#
#  $F = \exp(-3.7614 + 2.6718 \cdot \ln(SL))$ 
# calculating exp(2.6718)
exp(-3.7614)

## [1] 0.02325117

# if we plot the value on the equation
# We get the final equation is  $F = 0.02325 SL^{2.6877}$ 
# We can use this equation to predict the response variable, y, based on
# the value of the predictor variable, x.

# plotting the data
```

```
ggplot(df, aes(x =SL_mm , y = Fecundity)) + geom_point()+geom_smooth(met
hod='auto',formula = df$Fecundity ~ 2.6718(df$SL_mm^2.6718) )
## `geom_smooth()` using method = 'loess'
## Warning: Computation failed in `stat_smooth()`:
## attempt to apply non-function
```



```
model_bw <- lm(df$Fecundity ~ df$BW)
summary(model_bw)
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = df$Fecundity ~ df$BW)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -778.98 -245.49  -8.97   229.19  711.24
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -110.142     67.452  -1.633   0.105
## df$BW         212.760     6.567   32.399 <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 318.2 on 131 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.8891, Adjusted R-squared:  0.8882
## F-statistic: 1050 on 1 and 131 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
coef(model_bw)
## (Intercept)          df$BW
##  -110.1416         212.7598
```

The overall F-value of the model is 1050 and the corresponding p-value is extremely small ($< 2.2e-16$), which indicates that the model as a whole is significant.

The estimated Model is: $F = 212BW - 110$

```
ggplot(df, aes(x = BW , y = Fecundity)) + geom_point()+geom_smooth(method = 'lm', se = TRUE)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```

